

Flocculation and Cation Retention Studies of Different Humic Acid Fractions

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Coagulation studies reveal that metals in the same valency state are not identical in their interactions with soil organic matter and the coagulation power follows the sequence $\text{Co}^{2+} < \text{Ni}^{2+} < \text{Zn}^{2+} < \text{Cu}^{2+}$ irrespective of the pH of solution. Coagulation values of a particular cation are of the same order for soil humic acids isolated from different sources.

A comparison of bound metal retention data shows the following sequence $\text{Co}^{2+} < \text{Ni}^{2+} < \text{Cu}^{2+} < \text{Zn}^{2+}$ irrespective of the source and composition of soil humic acids.

STUDIES of flocculation, peptization and precipitation reactions reveal that soil organic matter metal interactions form sols, insoluble polymeric complexes and gels¹. The reactions are markedly influenced by the pH and oxidation-reduction status of the medium. Deb² pointed out that mutual coagulation and peptization occurred when organic matter extracts were mixed with iron oxide.

The retention of polyvalent cations by soil organic matters is due in part to the formation of complexes, some of which may be chelated, and simple salt formation when carboxylic acids is not remote. Though cation retention values are influenced by valency of ions, complexing tendency is a factor which affects the amount of retention, and it has a great importance from the standpoint of plant nutrition.

In the present work attempts are made to evaluate the amount of fixed or bound metal in different humic acid fractions and also their coagulation power isolated from two Indian soils of alluvial locality.

Experimental

Humic acid was extracted from Chinsura soil (alluvial locality), fractionated and purified by the standard procedure³.

To 3 ml. of aliquots (0.2 mg/ml) of aqueous solution of MSO_4 ($M = \text{Cu}, \text{Ni}, \text{Co}$ or Zn) in a series of ground glass-stoppered 25 ml conical flasks increasing volumes of organic matter solutions were added. Each system was diluted to approximately 12 ml with distilled water and adjusted with 0.1N NaOH or HCl solution to pH 3, 5 and 7 respectively and made finally to a volume of 15 ml with distilled water after shaking vigorously. On standing at room temperature for 24 hr, each system was checked for flocculation.

The metal complexing power of organic matters were measured in the following way :

To different organic sols a definite volume of standard MSO_4 solutions were added. The pH of these solutions were adjusted to 4 (approx.). These solutions were made to a definite volume so that organic matter concentrations remained approximately 0.1%, shaken in a mechanical shaker for 4 hr at room temperature and kept overnight for attainment of equilibrium. The mixtures were then centrifuged and clear solutions (leachate 1) collected. To the residues left after centrifuging the mixture, NaCl (N) solutions were added, made upto a definite volume, shaken for 4 hr and kept overnight. These mixtures were then centrifuged (leachate 2) and washed with acidulated water (pH 4). The leachates (1 and 2) together with respective washings were analysed with E.D.T.A. using solochrome black indicator at pH 10 (NH_4Cl and NH_4OH buffer).

Results and Discussion

Coagulation studies :

The minimum amounts of metal cations required to coagulate humic acids, expressed as mg of metal/g of organic matter (O.M.) (Table 1) are taken as the index of coagulation value. Coagulation data indicate that the metals of the same valency state are not identical in their capacity to cause coagulation. The order of increasing effectiveness in causing coagulation follows the sequences $\text{Co}^{2+} < \text{Ni}^{2+} < \text{Zn}^{2+} < \text{Cu}^{2+}$ which is also the finding of Khan⁴.

TABLE I. METAL COMPLEXING POWER OF SOIL ORGANIC MATTERS
(mg of metal/g of organic matter)

Soil	Organic matter fraction	Co^{2+}	Ni^{2+}	Zn^{2+}	Cu^{2+}
Chinsura	Humic acid	847	827	705	325
"	Hymato-melanic acid	646	602	493	182
Jalpaiguri	Humic acid	842	817	702	317
"	Hymato-melanic acid	632	587	475	170

The data in Table 1 reveal that soil organic matters behave as negatively charged colloid. The reaction of humates with sesquioxides involves an exchange between the cation and a portion of the functional groups of organic matters and the ionic groups of the sesquioxide micelle¹. The idea of such intramolecular bond formation gains support from the work of Aleksandrova⁵. Martin⁶ showed precipitation of humus metal sol as a result of the interactions between negatively charged organic colloid and polymeric forms of metal hydrous oxide containing a large number of positively charged spots in the pH range 4.0 and 5.0. These reactions depend on pH of the solution. Below pH 3.5, flocculation is caused by free metal ions but the exchange of humus anion on the surface of freshly formed metal hydrous oxide occurs at pH > 4.5⁶. Martin⁷ also showed that although Fe²⁺ displaces exchangeable hydrogen from humus at low pH, at pH > 3.0 humate anion replaces hydroxyl groups on iron oxide occurring as dimer in the system.

The present study showed that coagulation values are not altered due to pH change and supports the earlier finding⁸.

The coagulation values of any particular cation are of the same order for humic acids isolated from two different sources. This indicates a similarity in the behaviour of humic acids under study towards a given cation. Further, the same sequence in causing coagulation is followed by both the humic acid fractions, although actual amount of metal cations required to coagulate a definite weight of organic matter is different possibly due to their difference in molecular weight. However, this method does not give any useful information regarding coagulating power of water soluble fulvic acid fraction though Ponomarev⁹ observed that precipitation of colloidal compounds of fulvic acid and iron occurred in the pH range 5.8-5.9 with a fulvic acid iron ratio 1:12 and at pH 4.5 fulvic acid aluminium ratio 1:3.

Cation retention studies :

The amount of fixed or bound metal/gm of different soil organic matters are shown in Table 2. It appears that for a definite weight of soil organic matter the amount of fixed metal follows the sequence Co²⁺ < Ni²⁺ < Cu²⁺ < Zn²⁺. It was reported by Schlichting¹⁰ that although fairly high quantities of added copper was bound in different humic acids (2.17-2.54 meq/100 gm of dry organic matter) but was scarcely

fixed (0.07-1.15 meq/100 gm of dry organic matter). In the present study, however, fairly high quantities of metals are bound in functional sites present in soil organic matters and are not released by 1(N) NaCl solution. This increase in quantity of fixed

TABLE 2. CATION RETENTION OF SOIL ORGANIC MATTERS
(mg of fixed or bound metal/g of organic matter)

Soil	Organic matter fraction	Co ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	Zn ²⁺	Cu ²⁺
Chinsura	Humic acid	6.93	7.25	18.90	8.69
"	Hymato-melanic acid	5.02	5.37	14.63	6.71
Jalpaiguri	Humic acid	6.61	7.05	17.25	8.42
"	Hymato-melanic acid	4.91	5.22	13.87	6.52

metal bound to humic acids under study may be due to the presence of greater number of functional sites available for metallic interaction. The number of such complexing sites may be three or even more which can hold up metal ions by strong forces¹¹. The amount of fixed or bound metal is maximum in case of Zn and minimum for Ni or Co. Due to amphoteric character Zn²⁺ ions readily undergo hydrolysis to a marked extent to produce Zn(OH)⁺ species which react with carboxylic groups present in soil organic matters but the hydrolysis is suppressed in case of Cu²⁺ and much less for Ni²⁺ and Co²⁺. Owing to this smaller percentage Ni(OH)⁺ or Co(OH)⁺ can interact with carboxylate ions. It appears from this study that different soil organic matter fractions interact with hydroxylated metallic cations to produce organo-metallic complex and this view is in accordance with the findings of previous workers^{4,7,8}.

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